

A SEPARATE MODALITY PROCESSING WITH CASCADING ARCHITECTURE BY EMBEDDING INVERSION OF LATENCY(IOL) ML TO IMPROVE PERCEIVED LATENCY FOR BETTER PERFORMANCE AND STREAMING OF THE DATA

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Abstract:

In recent times the research on healthcare doctor recommendation systems are increasingly designed with relatively low-latency where the patient's interaction with the doctor's recommendation system have been very slow due to network issues and low capabilities as far as the design models are concerned. In this regard there is a great need where certain machine learning models need to be leveraged to handle patient-doctor matching efficiently. A collaborative machine learning models with collaborative filtering is needed to match patients with specialists' doctors is needed by minimizing the service delay. This can really be achieved by increasing the latency in terms of the design of the system by incorporating Inversion of Latency (IOL) by cascading Machine learning model (Reinforcement ML) with existing queuing models for better transmission of streaming data. This will really improvise a means for interacting with the patients with various specialist doctors based on the type of the disease and the diagnosed reports. This cascading model will improve the continuous interaction of various activities of the patient with respect to specialist doctor's recommendation system without any delay in the interaction due to IOL machine learning model. This will really improve the performance of the system with very much minimal delay in network data transmissions.

Keywords: Recommender Systems, machine learning, latency, Cascading models, Multimodal Data, Multimodal Fusion.

1. Introduction:

In the current landscape of online data services, the control of data transmission and cloud computing is often fragmented between ISPs and cloud providers. This separation leads to substantial cooperation challenges and suboptimal optimization for global data services. ISPs and cloud providers operate distinct infrastructures and pursue different profit patterns, resulting in diverse approaches to support online data services with varying service requirements. The quality of experience with the system will always help the users in improving the quality of service of the users. The doctor's recommendation system based on the diagnosis of the disease of the patient is really needed for better interaction without any delay in getting the service of the doctors. In this context the machine leaning models have to be modified and be embedded in the existing system. The queuing models which are defined for existing scenarios will consume a lot of time and there by latency and there by the interactions be delayed and thus the performance be degraded. The networking systems almost have zero tolerance for high latency where the delay of the transactions are very much maximal. On other hand the machine learning users will ensure the data flow based on the controllability of the data between networks advancements, it is important to note that certain critical medical services, such as real-time patient monitoring, virtual consultations and Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR) based surgeries [2, 3] which require low latency and intensive computation, may still face challenges in meeting their requirements. In recent

years, numerous researchers have explored the potential of cloud computing in the IoT and cloud based healthcare domains to provide intelligent medical services [4–9]. However, healthcare cloud platforms face a unique challenge with high latency in many scenarios, which is particularly unacceptable due to the potential risks it poses to patient’s health and even their lives. Some studies propose the use of fog computing-based healthcare systems to minimize latency between medical IoT devices and cloud. However the deployment of machine learning models with embedding aspects has a critical role to be played in avoiding the delays in the network. The queuing models which are existed sometimes may block the transactions of the impatient patient’s transactions because of the unexpected delays in the network due to the congestion of the data. One of the unique advantages of healthcare cloud is that both the transmission network and cloud services are controlled by the hospital’s IT department, which enables effective joint optimization of end-to-end latency and computational resources while ensuring statistical latency guarantees within local IoT and private cloud network. We introduce a central controller that dynamically adjusts bandwidth and computation speed on a global scale. Specifically, allocating more bandwidth resources corresponds to lower transmission latency, while faster computation speed leads to reduced processing latency. We model the process of ML devices accessing ML services as a tandem queue. The primary objective of this paper is to ensure that the service latency remains below the specified latency requirement for medical services, while minimizing the utilization of communication and computation resources. To achieve this, we employ EMBEDDED ML with Cascading architectures, which is a natural choice for addressing sequential decision-making problems. Through this model we develop an intelligent policy for the controller that automatically regulates the transmission rate and computation speed in an optimal manner.

2. Existing architecture:

The existing architecture will able to handle the patient’s activities within a sequential mode. In order to implement this the existing architecture uses two stage tandem queuing model where the activities are handled sequentially and any impatient patient wants to interact needed specialist doctor he may either be blocked or be kept under waiting queue for a long time. This situation sometimes creates a confusion state in the network domain where the Machine learning models may not be able to take the decisions in selecting a right path. The existing model may not maximize the latency in the network due to its sequential processing of the activities performed by the impatient patients based on the diagnosis of the disease. This will really demand the machine learning users to improve the latency so that interactions of the impatient patients will be maximized.

Fig.1: Two Stage queuing model in Machine Learning model

3. Proposed architecture:

Fig.2: Parallel processing Model with cascading architectures using Low Latency

The proposed architecture is addressed on the lines of improving the latency in the network with maximal interaction so the impatient patient’s interaction with the system. The existing two stage queuing model doesn’t handle the latency efficiently as it only handles the set of activities sequentially. An analogous parallel model is introduced in the existing model where the impatient patient’s interactions can be handled effectively. Whenever such patient’s want to interact with the system model, the design of the model will dynamically accept the request by incorporating the embedded cascading architecture of the ML models for better utilization of the network. This will really improve the latency of the system and there by the performance of the system.

4. Related work:

Due to the increasing adoption of ML and cloud-based healthcare systems, numerous researchers have focused on leveraging Machine Learning models to enable intelligent medical services. This will really lead to enhance the experiences of patients and improving the efficiency of healthcare providers. The existing models have been developed a human activity detection application capable of handling data from diverse machine learning models. The models in the monitoring environment will provide a semantic detection of activities and requirements from various patients. An augmented data set is introduced in order to detect and identify the set of requirements of the various patients from time to time. An analogous parallel model has been incorporated so as to deny the sequential processing and enhance the parallel mode of handling the requests from various patients. The proposed model will handle the patient’s requests from various sources and evaluate them through filtering and matching criteria. The matched data will be processed and be sent to the doctor’s recommendation module for improving the feasibility study for analyzing and recommending a specialized doctor for the patient. In this context the proposed model will minimize the latency of patient’s request and improve the better interaction with the system environment and thus improve the performance of the system.

However, addressing latency requirements remains a challenging problem that, if not effectively resolved, can result in serious medical negligence. Consequently, researchers have engaged in extensive research to find solutions for reducing latency in Machine Learning environment. By using virtual machine partitioning technology to significantly reduce latency and improve network usage. They also proposed a user authentication method to protect patient privacy through an identity management system.

Fig.3: Low Latency with Machine Learning Module

4.1 Problem Formulation:

In following proposed system model a parallel processing model is proposed. It addresses the different flow of the data related to the patient and doctors working in various hospitals. The data flow corresponding to the impatient patients have been collaborated and calibrated as per the machine learning domain. The reinforcement machine learning model will implement the inversion of latency where the system design will enable the heterogeneous activities in a defined manner. The IOL will fetch the data from various datasets of the impatient patient data such that these patients will be setup under the queue and based on the time stamp defined in the database the transactions are initiated so as to get the data from doctor's recommendation data sets. The data will be verified and matched after filtering and the data which is relevant will be sent to the dataflow module for relevant addressing of the doctor in health care recommendation system. For this to get happen various resources management systems must be put under existence to avoid any delay in service. Denial of service must be minimum with maximal inversion of latency. This will really improve the utilization of the networking with maximum through put. The model has been improvised by implementing parallel processing model where cascading of different machine learning models is incorporated in the proposed IOL model. The cascading architectures or models will recall track the input and output of various modules so as to avoid the denial of service and improve the quality of the service to the maximum extent.

4.2 Latency in the communication queue:

The transmission rate governs the waiting time of tasks in the communication queue. A higher transfer rate generally facilitates faster movement of tasks through the communication queue, thereby reducing communication delays.

Potential resource contention:

However, higher transfer rates may lead to contention with other tasks or service resources, which could increase overall latency in certain cases. Selection of computation speed (s) influences latency in the computation queue and resource utilization and contention.

Latency in the computation queue: Computation speed directly correlates to the processing time of tasks in the computation queue and results in higher computing speed.

Resource utilization and contention:

Nevertheless, opting for a higher computation speed might entail increased resource consumption, possibly resulting in less efficient resource utilization and subsequently augmenting the overall latency between communication and computation. In conclusion, the selection of transmission rate and computation speed necessitates a trade-off process that involves comprehensive consideration of the communication queue and computation queue characteristics to minimize overall system delay. The optimal balance between these two factors depends on specific problem requirements.

In this section, we present the experimental settings, train the ML model in a predefined environment, and run up a series of comparison experiments to demonstrate the rationality and validity of our proposed model. Given the absence of a terminal state in our problem, we introduce a variable to halt the learning process within an episode if the number of time steps exceeds certain threshold. At the onset of each episode, we initialize the environment to encompass a diverse range of states.

5 Experiment results

We conduct training for our ML and parallel processing model within the predefined environment, and convergence of average service latency, average resource score, and average reward per time step as a function of episodes

Training parameters		
Parameter	Actor	Critic
No. of Linear nodes	32	32
Activation function	ReLU	ReLU
Output Function	Tanh	Linear
Learning rate	0.0001	0.001
Batch size	128	128

Fig.4. Results of average service latency, average resource score and average reward per time step

6 Conclusion:

In the context of a Machine learning based healthcare system that offers real-time and computation-intensive medical services, a significant challenge arises in achieving the dual objectives of meeting medical service latency requirements while minimizing resource utilization. In this study, we address this challenge by formulating the problem parallel processing model with cascading architectures and employing Inversion of Latency. This model enables automatic adjustment of the transmission rate and computation speed, thereby ensuring the fulfillment of latency requirements while conserving resources. To evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of our proposed model, we conduct extensive comparison experiments. These experiments aim to validate the model's ability to appropriately allocate resources and demonstrate its superiority over alternative approaches. Furthermore, as part of our future work, we intend to explore the feasibility of applying our model to a cloud-fog based healthcare system. This investigation will enable us to assess the adaptability and performance of our proposed.

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